

Developing Intercultural Competence through Language Learning in a Military Context

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ABSTRACT

The article describes issues related to developing intercultural competence through language learning in a military context. As well as, the article studies the problem of using intercultural communicative method and provides opinions of the scholars on this topic. The idea of the priority of intercultural competence in teaching foreign languages is substantiated. Teaching intercultural communication in foreign language classes for cadets has the great importance in their future professional area and this is quite relevant at the present stage. The basis of learning intercultural communication is the ability to establish connections with representatives of another culture and language, the ability to find suitable forms of communication in any language. Quite often it is difficult to do this even in native language, when the intentions and actions of the interlocutor are known, so learning a foreign language is very difficult, since the interlocutors do not always understand each other.

Keywords: intercultural communication, foreign language, cadets, culture, language, native language, developing intercultural competence.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, as a result of the rapid development of intercultural communication and global transformations taking place in the world, there is an urgent need to create a new paradigm of education. Modern society urgently needs specialists with knowledge of a foreign language for professionally significant purposes, using language as a means of communication with colleagues - representatives of different cultures and nations. As English is the primary means of communication for a multinational, multicultural audience, both on board and ashore. To achieve

successful intercultural communication, such specialists need the ability to effectively solve problems that inevitably arise in the process of communication between people belonging to different national cultures. For full-fledged intercultural communication and mutual understanding, a specialist must have developed foreign language intercultural competence in the field of professional communication, by which we mean a set of knowledge about native and foreign language cultures, abilities and skills to understand and adequately use intercultural vocabulary in speech, to apply knowledge about the culture of native speakers in professional directed situations of foreign language communication and the ability to participate in professional intercultural interaction.

Within the framework of a compulsory foreign language course, the task of developing foreign language intercultural competence of river school cadets seems difficult to achieve, but to solve it is possible to use the potential of additional education, for example, a language training center.

DISCUSSIONS

It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of competence and competency when interpreting this approach. Competence is a certain social requirement for the educational preparation of a student in order for him to perform productive activities in a certain field. Competence is a set of personal qualities of a student, determined by the specifics of his field of activity and his personal experience [2].

The performance of both the student and the teacher is assessed using a variety of competencies. The direction was based on the basic meaning of the new term, meaning “achieving a result,” which is the goal of a competency-based approach to the content of student learning.

A modern specialist must possess a number of key competencies. This:

- cultural – respectful and tolerant coexistence with representatives of other linguistic cultures;

- political and social – the ability to work in a team, feel responsibility when making decisions and implementing them, not create conflict situations, try to resolve them peacefully;
- communication – perfect command of both native and foreign languages;
- information – mastery of the basics of modern information technologies;
- educational – the ability for continuous self-education for professional and personal growth [5].

All these competencies are part of the professional competence of a specialist, allowing the individual to be more mobile in the labor market and have a sufficient level of social adaptation.

Considering the essential characteristics of competencies as components of professional competence, it is important to pay attention to the relationship between competence and knowledge, skills and abilities. If skills and abilities ensure the assimilation and application of knowledge, then the development of competencies constitutes the practical meaning of this knowledge for students. After all, competence and competencies are always manifested in practical activities. The competency-based orientation of training is expressed in the fact that the content of training includes only such program material that corresponds to the competencies required in real life circumstances.

Intercultural competence occupies a special place in the structure of a specialist's professional competence.

The works of I.I.Khaleeva, V.V. Safonova, A.L. Berdichevsky, S.G. Ter-Minasova, V.P. Furmanova, P.V. Sysoeva and others, which discuss issues of humanistically oriented education that promotes the development of the student's personality are devoted to the research and development of models for the development of intercultural competence. The philosophical aspect of the problem

of developing intercultural competence is presented in the works of M.M. Bakhtin, V.S. Biblera, M.S. Kagana, B.D. Parygina and others. Issues of the influence of a foreign language on the development, formation and education of the learner's personality are covered in the studies of N.V. Baryshnikova, A.L. Berdichevsky, I.L. Bim, I.A. Winter, N.D. Galskova, E.I. Passova and others.

These studies contribute to the accumulation and systematization of scientific information on the problem of developing intercultural competence. However, teachers experience serious difficulties associated with the insufficient development of this problem in relation to the tasks of professionally oriented training of specialists in specific fields, with the lack of a system-forming principle and practical methodological materials, without which it is impossible to form students' readiness to enter into dialogue of cultures and professional communication at the intercultural level. This is confirmed by data on the low level of development of intercultural competence among graduates of non-linguistic educational institutions for whom a foreign language is not a specialty. The actual aspect of the development of intercultural competence of students is not considered in the mentioned studies.

The concept of intercultural competence is interpreted differently by different researchers. Some understand this as a specific form of communication, others present this competence as the ultimate goal of the process of teaching foreign languages.

Under the intercultural competence of A.V. Khutorskoy understands the ability to interact, which is based on knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the process of intercultural and communicative contacts [5]. N.N. Vasilyeva defines intercultural competence as knowledge of the specific features of a particular society that influence the formation of an individual's behavior, the use of certain non-verbal components, based on national and cultural values, customs and traditions. [3].

According to the definition given by A.P. Sadokhin, intercultural competence is a complex of knowledge and skills of an individual that is used for an effective process of intercultural interaction while simultaneously checking the results of communication using feedback [5].

Thus, researchers whose focus is on the intercultural approach give different interpretations of intercultural competence. A number of scientists define it as the possibility and skill of peaceful existence of people in one society and the ability to take part in a different linguistic culture as well as the integration of knowledge and behavior patterns with awareness of the historicity of cultural processes, moreover, the readiness of the individual to participate in all processes occurring in the world, with full awareness of the world and history.

According to the position of A. Knapp-Potthoff, the basis of intercultural competence is the following structural elements:

1. Affective;
2. Cognitive;
3. Strategic.

The affective element consists of empathy and tolerance. The cognitive element is based on the integration of knowledge about the native culture and the culture of the country of the language being studied, including general cultural and communicative knowledge. As for the strategic element, it is based on the student's verbal, educational and research strategies [2]. An important result of the study by E.V. Malkova came up with the concept of "reflection", expanding the structure and content of the strategic element of intercultural competence. According to her the individual has the opportunity to give his assessment of the world when entering into reflection [3].

On the components of intercultural competence A.Yu. Muratov defines as:

- knowledge (about cultural values, paralinguistic means of communication, communication norms, facts about culture, language knowledge);

- skills (assimilation of new knowledge, critical assessment, practical application of knowledge, correlation of events, interpretation of cultural facts);
- mental operations (cognition on the border of cultures, equivalence of cultures, critical view);
- attitude (openness, curiosity, rejection of prejudices, acceptance of culture).

Mastery of these components prepares a specialist to perceive changes taking place in the professional sphere in other countries and creates conditions for professional self-realization.

G.V.Elizarova puts forward intercultural competence as a learning goal as an asset of a linguistic personality. Moreover, the author identifies an intercultural aspect in each component of communicative competence [4], and the key concepts for it are knowledge and the ability to perform any action and the organization of a discussion of general significance, which is based on intercultural communication [5], i.e. mutual understanding between representatives of different cultures. Consequently, the experience of applying national and cultural knowledge in practice helps to overcome xenophobia, develop tolerance and promote mutual understanding between representatives of different linguistic and cultural communities. Regional knowledge is considered by modern science as a component of cultural studies [2] and, accordingly, sociocultural competence. In relation to the training of cadets of navigation faculties, introduction to professional background knowledge, i.e. knowledge for social groups is mandatory within the profile being studied for successful professional communication in the target language.

Solving the problem of developing foreign language intercultural competence presupposes the need to study individual components of this competence in order to develop an effective methodology for students to master it. In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, there are different views on the structural components of intercultural competence.

CONCLUSIONS

Having analyzed different points of view on the content of the components that make up intercultural competence, we tried to present the knowledge, abilities, skills, abilities that are part of foreign language intercultural competence.

Thus, the systematic use of professional knowledge, foreign language skills and abilities in the context of practiced intercultural communicative speech situations using interactive forms, techniques and teaching methods ensures the integration of technical and humanitarian disciplines. This approach will improve the competitiveness of domestic specialists and cadets of military educational institutions. And professional foreign language communicative competence, being a component of the professional competence of a specialist, allows for adequate and successful every day and professional foreign language communication.

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